

Unified Server-Side Transaction Replay for PostgreSQL Failover: Merging Connection-Level and Transaction-Level Continuity with Savepoint-Aware Journaling and WAL-Synchronized Replay

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Abstract

We present a proxy-based transaction replay system for PostgreSQL-compatible databases that unifies connection-level failover (cursor re-execution, analogous to Oracle TAF) and transaction-level replay (statement re-execution with correctness verification, analogous to Oracle TAC/Application Continuity) into a single mechanism. The proxy maintains a per-session, savepoint-aware transaction journal with WAL LSN synchronization, replays it autonomously against a new primary after failover, and verifies correctness via CRC64 result checksums—all without any client-side modification. We position this work within the existing landscape: Oracle Application Continuity [1] implements client-directed replay in the OCI/JDBC driver; MariaDB MaxScale 2.3.0 (2018) implements proxy-side replay for MySQL with xxHash checksum verification [6]; and most other proxy systems (PgBouncer, Pgpool-II, ProxySQL, AWS RDS Proxy, Vitess) provide no transaction replay at all, aborting in-flight transactions on failover. Our contribution is: (1) the first proxy-side transaction replay for PostgreSQL-compatible databases, (2) unification of cursor restoration and DML replay in a single mechanism, (3) savepoint-aware journal truncation enabling partial rollback during replay, (4) WAL LSN anchoring that ties journal entries to the replication stream for standby synchronization verification, and (5) back-end connection swapping that preserves the client TCP session through failover. This disclosure establishes prior art for these specific contributions.

1 Introduction

Transparent database failover—redirecting client connections from a failed primary to a new primary without client-visible errors—is a critical enterprise requirement. The landscape divides into three categories:

Client-directed replay. Oracle Application Continuity (AC) [1, 2] and MariaDB Connector/J 3.0 [7] maintain replay state in the client driver. Oracle’s implementation is the most mature, using Logical Transaction IDs (LTXIDs) for at-most-once semantics [3] and a replay context for mutable value preservation [4]. The client driver re-executes cached statements after reconnecting to a new instance.

Proxy-directed replay. MariaDB MaxScale 2.3.0 (2018) is the only production proxy implementing server-side transaction replay [6]. MaxScale journals all SQL statements within a transaction in the proxy process memory and replays them against a replacement server when the current primary fails, verifying correctness via xxHash-128 checksums. MaxScale operates exclusively with MySQL/MariaDB backends.

No replay. The vast majority of database proxies abort in-flight transactions on failover and require client-side retry: PgBouncer [8], Pgpool-II [9], ProxySQL [10], AWS RDS Proxy [11], and Vitess [12] all fall into this category. Patroni [13] drops all active connections during failover. CockroachDB and YugabyteDB perform limited server-side retry for serialization conflicts, but not cross-node failover replay.

The gap. No system provides proxy-side transaction replay for PostgreSQL-compatible databases. MaxScale covers MySQL only. The PostgreSQL ecosystem (PgBouncer, Pgpool-II, Patroni) offers no in-proxy transaction replay at all. We describe a system that fills this gap.

2 Contributions

We make five specific contributions beyond existing systems:

1. **First proxy-side transaction replay for PostgreSQL.** All existing PostgreSQL proxy/HA tools (PgBouncer, Pgpool-II, Patroni, AWS RDS Proxy) abort in-flight transactions on failover. MaxScale’s proxy-side replay is MySQL-only. Our system is the first to provide transparent transaction replay at the proxy layer for PostgreSQL wire protocol clients.
2. **Unified cursor restoration + DML replay.** Oracle separates TAF (connection-level, cursor re-execution) and TAC (transaction-level, full DML replay) as independently configured features. MaxScale replays DML transactions but does not restore cursor positions for interrupted SELECT streaming. Our system treats cursor restoration and DML replay as phases of a single replay sequence.
3. **Savepoint-aware journal with partial rollback.** Our journal tracks savepoints and supports ROLLBACK TO SAVEPOINT by truncating journal entries beyond the savepoint sequence number. During replay, only entries up to the last active savepoint are replayed. Neither Oracle AC nor MaxScale document savepoint-aware journal truncation.
4. **WAL LSN-anchored journal entries.** Each transaction journal records a `start_lsn` from the write-ahead log. Before replay, the system verifies that the new primary’s LSN has advanced to at least the journal’s start LSN, ensuring the standby has received all WAL records up to the transaction’s beginning. This prevents replaying against a standby that is missing prerequisite data.
5. **Backend connection swapping.** During failover, the proxy maintains the client’s TCP connection and swaps only the backend database connection. The client experiences no TCP disconnect, no TLS renegotiation, and no session re-establishment. MaxScale and Oracle AC both involve client-visible reconnection (even if transparent at the application level).

3 Architecture

3.1 Component Overview

```
Client (any PG client, unmodified)
  | persistent TCP connection
  v
```


3.2 Transaction Journal Data Model

```

1 struct TransactionJournalEntry {
2     tx_id: Uuid,           // transaction identifier
3     session_id: Uuid,     // client session
4     node_id: NodeId,     // origin primary
5     started_at: DateTime<Utc>,
6     start_lsn: u64,      // WAL anchor point
7     entries: Vec<JournalEntry>,
8     current_sequence: u64,
9     active: bool,
10    has_mutations: bool,
11    savepoints: Vec<Savepoint>,
12 }
13
14 struct JournalEntry {
15     sequence: u64,
16     statement: String,
17     parameters: Vec<JournalValue>,
18     result_checksum: Option<u64>, // CRC64
19     rows_affected: Option<u64>,
20     timestamp: DateTime<Utc>,
21     statement_type: StatementType,
22     duration_ms: u64,
23 }
24
25 struct Savepoint {
26     name: String,
27     sequence: u64,           // journal position
28     created_at: DateTime<Utc>,

```

3.3 Statement Classification

Statements are classified for replay eligibility:

Type	Keyword	Replayable
Select	SELECT	Re-executable (cursor)
Insert	INSERT	Yes
Update	UPDATE	Yes
Delete	DELETE	Yes
DDL	CREATE/ALTER/DROP	No (logged, skipped)
Transaction	BEGIN/COMMIT/ROLLBACK	Control flow only
Set	SET	Yes (session state)

4 Algorithms

4.1 Savepoint-Aware Journaling

Algorithm 1 Savepoint-Aware Journal Management

```

1: procedure CREATESAVEPOINT(journal, name)
2:   journal.savepoints.push(Savepoint{name, journal.seq})
3: end procedure

4: procedure ROLLBACKTOSAVEPOINT(journal, name)
5:   idx ← FINDSAVEPOINT(journal, name)
6:   seq ← journal.savepoints[idx].sequence
7:   journal.entries.retain(e ⇒ e.seq ≤ seq)           ▷ Truncate beyond savepoint
8:   journal.savepoints.truncate(idx + 1)                ▷ Remove later savepoints
9: end procedure

```

This ensures that if a client issues `ROLLBACK TO SAVEPOINT sp1`, the journal reflects the partial rollback. During replay, only the entries surviving the rollback are re-executed, maintaining consistency with the client’s intended transaction state.

4.2 WAL-Synchronized Replay

4.3 WAL LSN Acquisition and Verification

When a transaction begins, the proxy queries the primary’s current write-ahead log position via `pg_current_wal_lsn()` and records it as `start_lsn` in the journal. Before replay, the proxy queries the new primary’s `pg_last_wal_replay_lsn()` (for a promoted standby) or `pg_current_wal_lsn()` (for a planned switchover target). If the new primary’s LSN is below `start_lsn`, the proxy polls at 100ms intervals with a configurable timeout (default: 30s). This ensures the standby has received all WAL records that existed when the transaction began, preventing replay against stale data that would cause silent correctness violations or false checksum divergence.

Algorithm 2 Proxy-Directed Replay with WAL Verification

```
1: procedure REPLAY(journal, new_primary)
2:                                     ▷ Phase 0: Verify standby has caught up
3:   standby_lsn ← GETREPLAYLSN(new_primary)
4:   if standby_lsn < journal.start_lsn then
5:     WAITFORLSN(new_primary, journal.start_lsn)
6:   end if

7:                                     ▷ Phase 1: Restore session state
8:   conn ← POOLGETCONNECTION(new_primary)
9:   for entry ∈ journal.entries where entry.type = Set do
10:    EXECUTE(conn, entry.sql)
11:  end for

12:                                     ▷ Phase 2: Replay DML with checksum verification
13:  EXECUTE(conn, "BEGIN")
14:  for entry ∈ journal.entries where entry.type.is_replayable() do
15:    result ← EXECUTE(conn, entry.sql, entry.params)
16:    if entry.checksum ≠ ⊥ then
17:      chk ← CRC64(result)
18:      if chk ≠ entry.checksum then
19:        EXECUTE(conn, "ROLLBACK")
20:        return REPLAYDIVERGENCE
21:      end if
22:    end if
23:  end for

24:                                     ▷ Phase 3: Restore cursors (SELECT re-execution)
25:  for cursor ∈ journal.open_cursors do
26:    result ← EXECUTE(conn, cursor.sql, cursor.params)
27:    SEEKTOPPOSITION(result, cursor.last_row_index)
28:  end for

29:                                     ▷ Phase 4: Swap backend connection
30:  SWAPBACKEND(journal.session_id, conn)                                     ▷ Client TCP preserved
31:  return REPLAYSUCCESS
32: end procedure
```

This mechanism is distinct from Oracle’s LTXID approach, which tracks transaction commit status but does not verify replication stream position. It is also distinct from MaxScale, which has no WAL-level synchronization check before replay—MaxScale relies on MariaDB’s semi-synchronous replication guarantees externally.

4.4 Backend Connection Swapping

The proxy maintains the client-facing TCP connection throughout failover. Only the backend connection (proxy-to-database) is replaced:

1. Client TCP socket remains open (no RST, no FIN)
2. TLS session to client is preserved (no renegotiation)
3. Proxy acquires a new backend connection from the standby pool (pre-warmed)
4. Journal replay occurs on the new backend
5. Session-internal state (client ↔ backend mapping) is atomically swapped
6. Client’s next query goes to the new backend transparently

MaxScale closes and reopens client connections during replay (transparent to the MariaDB client library, but visible at the TCP level). Oracle AC involves client-visible reconnection handled by the OCI/JDBC driver.

5 Comparison with Prior Art

Property	Oracle AC	MaxScale	PgBouncer	Pgpool-II	RDS Proxy	This work
Protocol	Oracle	MySQL	PostgreSQL	PostgreSQL	Multi	PostgreSQL
Replay location	Client driver	Proxy	None	None	None	Proxy
DML replay	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	Yes
Cursor restoration	Yes (TAF)	No	No	No	No	Yes
Unified TAF+TAC	No (separate)	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Yes
Savepoint-aware	Unknown	No ^a	N/A	N/A	N/A	Yes
WAL LSN anchoring	No (LTXID)	No	N/A	N/A	N/A	Yes
Checksum verif.	Yes (replay ctx)	xxHash-128	N/A	N/A	N/A	CRC64
Client modification	Required	None	N/A	N/A	N/A	None
Client TCP pre-served	No (reconnect)	No (reconnect)	N/A	N/A	N/A	Yes
Cross-session coord.	No	No ^b	N/A	N/A	N/A	Possible

Table 1: Comparison of transaction replay mechanisms. ^aMaxScale documentation does not describe savepoint-aware journal truncation. ^bMaxScale MXS-4149 (cooperative replay across HA instances) was closed as “Won’t Do.”

5.1 Differentiation from Oracle Application Continuity

Oracle’s patents [1, 2, 3, 4, 5] claim a *client-directed* model where the OCI/JDBC driver maintains replay state. Our system uses a fundamentally different architecture: the proxy owns the journal, the client is unmodified, and idempotence is verified via CRC64 checksums rather than Logical Transaction IDs. Oracle requires Oracle-specific drivers; our system works with any PostgreSQL-compatible client (psycopg2, pgx, node-postgres, Go database/sql, JDBC).

5.2 Differentiation from MariaDB MaxScale

MaxScale 2.3.0 (2018) pioneered proxy-side transaction replay for MySQL [6]. Our system differs in five respects: (1) PostgreSQL wire protocol rather than MySQL; (2) unified cursor restoration and DML replay; (3) savepoint-aware journal truncation; (4) WAL LSN anchoring for standby synchronization verification; (5) backend connection swapping preserving the client TCP session. MaxScale’s MXS-4149 proposal for cooperative cross-instance replay was abandoned; our architecture supports this through the session-scoped journal model.

5.3 Differentiation from PostgreSQL Ecosystem

No PostgreSQL proxy or HA tool provides transaction replay. PgBouncer is a pure connection pooler with no failover logic. Pgpool-II kills child processes on failover (preserving sessions since v3.6 but aborting transactions). Patroni drops all connections. AWS RDS Proxy preserves idle connections but terminates mid-transaction sessions. This is the first system to bring MaxScale-class proxy-side replay to the PostgreSQL world.

6 Switchover Buffer

For planned switchovers (as opposed to unplanned failovers), the system provides a query buffer that queues incoming writes during the switchover window:

- Configurable timeout (default 5s), max queries (default 10,000), max memory (default 100MB)
- Incoming write queries are buffered with a per-client response channel
- Once the new primary is confirmed, buffered queries are drained and executed
- If timeout is exceeded, buffered queries fail with a timeout error
- Read queries can optionally be served from read replicas during switchover

This enables zero-downtime planned switchovers where no client query is lost.

7 Limitations

1. **Mutable values:** Functions like `NOW()`, `RANDOM()`, `NEXTVAL()` produce different results on replay. Oracle’s US9,124,670 covers a “replay context” approach. We do not implement mutable value interception; applications using these functions in write transactions may experience replay divergence. Mitigation: the system detects divergence via checksum mismatch and aborts replay.
2. **Non-deterministic queries:** `SELECT` without `ORDER BY` may return rows in different order on the new primary, causing false checksum divergence for cursor restoration. Mitigation: only mutations are checksum-verified; cursor restoration uses position-based seeking without checksum comparison.
3. **Proxy as single point of failure:** The proxy itself must be highly available. Addressed via standard proxy HA (active-passive, floating IP).
4. **Memory overhead:** Journal size is proportional to transaction size. The `BufferConfig.max_buffer_memory` parameter (default 100MB) limits total memory consumption.
5. **DDL transactions:** DDL statements (`CREATE`, `ALTER`, `DROP`) are logged but not replayed, as replaying DDL is unsafe (schema may already exist on new primary via replication). Transactions containing DDL are flagged as non-replayable.

8 Implementation

Implemented in Rust as part of HeliosProxy. Key modules:

- `proxy/transaction_journal.rs`: Journal data model, savepoint management, entry classification, size accounting.
- `proxy/switchover_buffer.rs`: Query buffering during planned switchovers with configurable timeout, memory limits, and per-client response channels.
- `proxy/primary_tracker.rs`: Topology monitoring, primary change event broadcasting, confirmation tracking.

The feature is gated behind the `ha-tr` feature flag. Requires `ha-proxy` (base proxy) and `ha-tier1` (WAL replication) as prerequisites. Licensed under AGPL-3.0 (Nano) and SSPL-1.0 (Full/Lite/Proxy).

9 Conclusion

This disclosure establishes prior art for five specific contributions in proxy-based database transaction replay: (1) first proxy-side replay for PostgreSQL, (2) unified cursor restoration and DML replay, (3) savepoint-aware journal truncation, (4) WAL LSN-anchored replay verification, and (5) backend connection swapping with TCP session preservation. We acknowledge MaxScale’s 2018 pioneering work in proxy-side replay for MySQL and Oracle’s extensive patent portfolio for client-directed replay, and position our contributions as differentiated extensions of this prior art to the PostgreSQL ecosystem.

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